

Sr. No.	Name of the Author	Title of the Paper	Pg.No.	PDF
01	Abhishek Das	Hindu: Activism, Aesthetics and the Future	01-05	PDF
02	Ajoy Batta	Franz Kafka: Envisioning Derridean Concepts	06-10	PDF
03	Altaf Ahmad Ganaie & Dr. R.S. Chauhan	Arundhati Roy's The God of Small Things: A Feminist Perspective	11-13	PDF
04	Anju Bala	Silence No More: A Study of Mahasweta Devi's Draupadi	14-16	PDF
05	S.A.Thameemul Ansari	Discourse on the Theme of 'Self-determinism' in Fourth World Literature	17-21	PDF
06	Arpita Prasad	Problematisation of the Image of Helen Keller in The Story of my Life	22-24	PDF
07	Anil Shrirang Awad	Acculturation of the Folk Dances:	25-30	PDF

Sr. No.	Name of the Author	Title of the Paper	Pg.No.	PDF
		Special Reference to Maharashtra		
08	Basanti Karmakar	Vijay Tendulkar's Kanyadaan: A Journey from Ignorance to Experience	31-35	PDF
09	Dr. Vandana Bhatt	The Chaos of the Melting Pot: Multiculturalism in Bharati Mukherjee's Fiction	36-39	PDF
10	Dr. Mohd Shafi Dar & Rashma Siraj	Acculturation in the Novels of V.S. Naipaul	40-45	PDF
11	Dr. Deepti Sharma	Caste System, the Scourge of Indian Civilization and Culture: Bama's Karukku	46-51	PDF
12	Farah Deeba Shafiq	Revitalizing the Tradition: Mahesh Dattani's Contribution to Indian English Drama	52-62	PDF
13	Imran Majeed Bhat	Theatre of the Absurd and Samuel Beckett	63-69	PDF
14	Irfan Mohammad Malik	Possession as a Fictional Hybrid: A.S Byatt's Tryst with Postmodernism	70-72	PDF
15	Finitha Jose	Children's Books Adaptations: A Reading of War Horse	73-79	PDF
16	Ravinder Kaur	Flaubert's Madame Bovary: A Paradigm of Lacanian Desire	80-85	PDF
17	Dr. (Mrs.) Prabha Vig & Komal Sharma	Comparative Analysis of Influence of Gender on Reading Interest of Inservice and Pre-service Teachers	86-101	PDF
18	Ihsan-ur-Rahim Malik	Shakespeare's Tragic Vision	102-105	PDF
19	Dr. Meenu Khyalia	Theme of Alienation in Shashi Deshpande's Moving On	106-111	PDF

Sr. No.	Name of the Author	Title of the Paper	Pg.No.	PDF
20	Saikat Nandi	Conrad's Treatment of Women in Heart of Darkness	112-115	PDF
21	Neelima V.	From Repudiation to Reconciliation: Mothers and Daughters in Amy Tan's The Joy Luck Club	116-119	PDF
22	Nibedita Bandyopadhyay	The Role of Science and Technology as a Metaphor in Pynchon's The Crying of Lot 49	120-123	PDF
23	Raul Palma	"All that David Copperfield kind of crap": The Explicit and Non-Explicit Unreliable Narrator	124-131	PDF
24	Pouya Gholamalipur & Mohammad Ali Alaeddini	Anti-Colonial Oscar Wilde: Homoeroticism in Classical Greece	132-140	PDF
25	Chinta Praveen Kumar	Guilty Pleasures	141-145	PDF
26	Raghul V. Rajan	The Politics of Liberation in Kanthapura and its Upshot in Train to Pakistan: A Fanonian Critique	146-152	PDF
27	Rajni Kant	Empowering Women: A Feminist Reading of Kamala Das' Works	153-160	PDF
28	Dr. T Narayana & BV Ramani	Human Elements in Gita Mehta's A River Sutra	161-166	PDF
29	Jayanta Rana	'Gendered Home' in the Short Stories of Shashi Deshpande	167-172	PDF
30	Reena Verma	Creative Use of Language in Keats's Odes: A Study in the light of Rīti Siddhānta (Theory of Style)	173-182	PDF
31	P.Renuga	The Evolution of Feminine Freedom: A Study of Shashi Deshpande's That Long Silence	183-185	PDF

Sr. No.	Name of the Author	Title of the Paper	Pg.No.	PDF
32	Reshu Gupta	Land and Landscape in Anita Desai's Cry, the Peacock	186-191	PDF
33	Ruchi Tomar	Mapping Subaltern Crisis in Arundhati Roy's The God of Small Things	192-196	PDF
34	Sadia Hasan	It's a SMALL's World: Children's Fiction in English	197-200	PDF
35	Ch.S.Sailaja	A Comparative Study of Achievement in Grammar and Performance on a Cross Word Puzzle in English Grammar	201-216	PDF
36	Santulan Mahanta	Mutual Dependence of Power and Language	217-220	PDF
37	Surajit Sen	Narrative Design of Ruskin Bond's The Blue Umbrella: A Todorovian Model	221-224	PDF
38	Anayat Shah	Odyssey of Education in Kashmir and the Emergence of English Language	225-231	PDF
39	Shaheena Akhtar	Small Remedies: Roads to Recovery	232-244	PDF
40	Dr. Shalini Yadav	Ethnic Transformation: Tara's Forever Revolving Identity in Bharati Mukherjee's Desirable Daughters	245-252	PDF
41	Dr. Sheeba Azhar & Dr. Syed Abid Ali	Teaching English in Professional Colleges of Saudi Arabia: Trends and Challenges	253-261	PDF
42	Beetoshok Singha	Kipling's Imperial Anxiety: A Study of The Strange Ride of Morrowbie Jukes	262-268	PDF
43	Dr.Sonia khandelwal	Technique in the Novels of Lawrence Durrell	269-281	PDF

Sr. No.	Name of the Author	Title of the Paper	Pg.No.	PDF
44	P.Subapradha & Dr. R. Shanthi	Gynocentric Perspective of Morag Gunn in Margaret Laurence's The Diviners	282-285	PDF
45	Dr. Sutanu Kumar Mahapatra	Nationhood, Secularism and Politics in Girish Karnad's Tughlaq	286-295	PDF
46	Dr. (Mrs) Jubanlak Sutnga	The Identity of the Artist: Michael Ondaatje's The Collected Works of Billy the Kid	296-305	PDF
47	Sakshi Thakur	Train to Pakistan: A Direct Gaze at the Ugliness of Partition	306-313	PDF
48	Vibhuti Wadhawan	Dualistic Modernity and the Illegitimacy of Nationalism in Tagore's The Home and the World	314-321	PDF
49	Gaganpreet Walia	The Role of Contexts in Textual Understanding of Literature	322-329	PDF
50	Wasia Mushtaq	Religion and Literature: A Poetic Interface	330-335	PDF
BOOK REVIEW				
01	Hiren Zala	All & Everything in Diagrams by Mohan Vaishnav	336	PDF
02	Syeda Shahzia Batool Naqvi	Silhouette of Reflections by Neelam Saxena Chandra	337-340	PDF
03	Dr Karanam R Rao	Mother's Veena and other Poems by Anna Sujatha Mathai	341-342	PDF
04	Nirjharini Tripathy	The Street by Ann Petry	343-349	PDF
05	Varsha Singh	Curse of the Kalingan by Shobha Nihalani	350-351	PDF
INTERVIEW				
01	Gulnaz Fatima	Gulnaz Fatima in Conversation with Ruskin Bond	352-357	PDF

Sr. No.	Name of the Author	Title of the Paper	Pg.No.	PDF
FICTION				
01	Arunabha Ghosh	The Notebook	358-362	PDF
02	Pratap Kumar Dash	The Lost Identity	363-371	PDF
03	Dr. Pushpa VK	Voiceless Voices...	372-375	PDF
POETRY				
01	Aashmika	Born	376-380	PDF
02	Pijush Kanti Deb	An Old Bi-Cycle	381-382	PDF
03	Diane Dehler	Anima/Animus	383	PDF
04	Dr. Anupam R. Nagar	Farewell	384	PDF
05	Peter Cowlam	Realpolitik	385	PDF
06	Prabhat Jha	A Young Man's Confession	386	PDF
07	Showkat Hussain Dar	My Homeland	387-388	PDF
08	G.H. Smith	Departures	389	PDF
09	Subham Ganguly	An Ode to My Confusions	390-391	PDF
10	Sukrita Paul Kumar	Resurrection	392	PDF
